

A HOMOTOPIC CONVEX OPTIMIZATION APPROACH FOR TRAJECTORY DESIGN IN MULTI-BODY MODELS

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The Moon is poised to be a key focus in human space exploration, with numerous missions planned in the near future. Spacecraft missions in the cislunar region require optimized trajectory and mission design within complex multi-body models. We propose a sequential convex programming (SCP) approach for designing trajectories with impulsive maneuvers in multi-body models and transitioning them into an ephemeris model. We make use of a pulsating-rotating frame and a homotopic approach to enhance convergence. The high accuracy and robustness make SCP an excellent alternative to nonlinear programming solvers, even for highly nonlinear problems.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, there has been increasing interest in missions to the Moon and beyond. NASA's Artemis program, for example, aims to establish an extended presence around the Moon and in lunar and cislunar space in the near future. Commercial ventures such as Blue Origin and Intuitive Machines have invested resources into developing economically viable and reliable lunar access. While trajectory design for unmanned missions is generally concerned with minimizing fuel expenditure as well as operational constraints, manned missions must assess time-of-flight, abort options, among others. Mission designers face significant challenges in optimizing for these requirements due to the complex gravitational interactions among multiple celestial bodies.

Over the last few decades, there have been substantial advancements in space mission design, particularly through the use of multi-body dynamics. This approach enables efficient transfers and orbits that were not possible with the traditional two-body Keplerian assumption. By approximating the complex environment using the gravitational influences of two or three primary bodies, we

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can gain valuable insights into the dynamical structures of a multi-body environment. The circular restricted three-body problem (CRTBP) is the most popular and most frequently used model for cislunar and lunar transfers because of its relatively low complexity [1]. Yet, it is a low-fidelity model, and its solutions do not represent the real dynamics sufficiently. Therefore, extensions have been proposed, such as the elliptic restricted three-body problem (ERTBP) and the bi-circular restricted four-body problem (BCRFBP) [2] to increase fidelity.

As finding optimal transfer trajectories directly from higher fidelity models is computationally challenging, much of prior research has relied on first generating favorable initial guess trajectories in the CRTBP. However, these trajectories often lose their favorable characteristics when transitioned to a higher fidelity model and require correction. Previous work has improved on this process at different stages, for example, Boudad et al. [3] leveraged the BCRFBP as an intermediate between the CRTBP and high-fidelity ephemeris models for Earth-Moon Near-Rectilinear Halo Orbits (NRHO) as direct transitions from the CRTBP to ephemeris model resulted in unfavorable solutions. Additionally, enhancing initial guesses with perturbations in the BCRFBP improved quasi-periodic orbits in the ephemeris model. More work by Boudad has focused on the stability properties of the NRHO within the BCRFBP as well as the change in its properties when transitioning to high-fidelity ephemeris models in the cislunar region [4, 5].

Beyond the cislunar region, the same process was used to generate trajectories to heliocentric orbits near the Sun-Earth L2 portal [6], as well as round-trip transfers near the Sun-Earth L1 and L2 portals [7] in the Sun-Earth-Moon BCRFBP. Scheuerle employed a similar strategy to Boudad by taking known traits of ballistic lunar transfers in the CRTBP [8] as well as generating families of their trajectories [9] to generate initial guesses in the BCRFBP before transitioning them to an ephemeris model. Continuing with ballistic lunar transfers, Scheuerle augmented the BCRFBP with low-thrust acceleration as a continuous force in order to find trajectories optimized for missions with limited propellant budget [10]. In further application, jettison and disposal trajectories from the NASA Gateway Station's NRHO orbit to heliocentric space were designed in the CRTBP and BCRFBP [11, 12]. Analysis by McCarthy [13] investigated quasi-periodic trajectories and their properties in the BCRFBP to construct Poincaré maps to design ballistic lunar transfers.

These works mainly use nonlinear programming (NLP) approaches to design optimal trajectories. While this has proven effective in many cases, the computational effort can be considerable, and a good initial guess is required to achieve convergence. In early mission design studies, often several hundred thousand potential trajectories must be explored. This makes NLP methods less viable due to the extensive computational effort. Given the large search space, a quick yet accurate method is needed to compute such trajectories rapidly. In recent years, methods based on convex optimization have become increasingly popular due to their lower computational effort and often larger convergence domain [14]. They are commonly used for interplanetary transfers in two-body dynamics and have recently been applied to problems in the CRTBP, for example for transfers between a nearly in-plane halo orbit and an NRHO [15], and halo-to-halo transfers [16]. Other works compute trajectories between butterfly orbits [17] and distant retrograde orbits (DRO) [18]. However, higher-fidelity models such as the BCRFBP and ephemeris model, which account for the gravity of additional planets, are often more beneficial for determining low-energy transfers in cislunar space that would not be possible with the CRTBP. When transitioning to an ephemeris model, sequential convex programming (SCP) may struggle to converge as the CRTBP solution may not be sufficient as an initial guess for a higher-fidelity model. At the same time, SCP often offers several advantages over other methods, including improved computational efficiency.

In this study, we address this gap in the ability to apply convex optimization techniques in higher-fidelity multi-body models as well as the gap in transitioning useful guesses in the CRTBP into higher fidelity models. We propose a homotopic approach for reliably and efficiently computing trajectories with impulsive maneuvers across various multi-body models. In particular, we consider the CRTBP, BCRFBP, and an ephemeris model in the rotating-pulsating frame (RPNBP). This work aims to enable more accurate and reliable trajectory design for cislunar missions, as well as to better achieve specific mission objectives.

The paper is organized as follows: first, we introduce the dynamical models and the rotating-pulsating frame; subsequently, we describe the homotopic approach and its incorporation into the SCP framework. Then, we present the simulations and results, and finally provide final remarks to conclude the paper.

DYNAMICAL MODELS

Similarly to the common CRTBP that uses a rotating frame where the two primaries are fixed points, we consider the general rotating-pulsating frame (RPF) in Fig. 1 to account for additional perturbing bodies. The points P_1 , P_2 , s/c , and A_j refer to the two primaries, the spacecraft, and additional perturbing bodies, respectively. B denotes the origin and the center of mass between the two primaries. Given an inertial frame where \mathbf{b} and \mathbf{r} denote the vectors from the origin to the barycenter B and spacecraft, respectively, and the vector $\mathbf{r}_{P_1 P_2}$ from P_1 to P_2 , the unit vectors $\hat{\mathbf{i}}_x$, $\hat{\mathbf{i}}_y$, and $\hat{\mathbf{i}}_z$ of the rotating-pulsating frame are defined as follows:

$$\hat{\mathbf{i}}_x(t) = \frac{\mathbf{r}_{P_1 P_2}(t)}{\|\mathbf{r}_{P_1 P_2}(t)\|} \quad (1)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{i}}_y(t) = \hat{\mathbf{i}}_z(t) \times \hat{\mathbf{i}}_x(t) \quad (2)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{i}}_z(t) = \frac{\mathbf{r}_{P_1 P_2}(t) \times \mathbf{v}_{P_1 P_2}(t)}{\|\mathbf{r}_{P_1 P_2}(t) \times \mathbf{v}_{P_1 P_2}(t)\|} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{v}_{P_1 P_2}(t) = d\mathbf{r}_{P_1 P_2}(t)/dt$. Defining $\ell(t) := \|\mathbf{r}_{P_1 P_2}(t)\|$, the transformation between the inertial and rotating-pulsating frame is then given by

$$\mathbf{r}(t) = \mathbf{b}(t) + \ell(t) \mathbf{C}(t) \boldsymbol{\rho}(\tau) \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{C}(t)$ is a rotation matrix:

$$\mathbf{C}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\mathbf{i}}_x(t) & \hat{\mathbf{i}}_y(t) & \hat{\mathbf{i}}_z(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

As the position $\boldsymbol{\rho}(\tau)$ and velocity $\boldsymbol{\rho}'(\tau)$ of the spacecraft in the RPF are nondimensional, it is convenient to introduce the corresponding derivatives with respect to the physical t and nondimensional time τ :

$$\frac{d\boldsymbol{\rho}}{dt} = \dot{\boldsymbol{\rho}} \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{d\boldsymbol{\rho}}{d\tau} = \boldsymbol{\rho}' \quad (7)$$

Figure 1: Rotating-pulsating frame.

where we use $(\dot{\cdot})$ and $(\cdot)'$ to denote the derivative with respect to t and τ , respectively. Note that the time dependency is omitted for readability. Their relationship is

$$\frac{d\boldsymbol{\rho}}{dt} = \frac{d\boldsymbol{\rho}}{d\tau} \frac{d\tau}{dt} = \boldsymbol{\rho}' \dot{\tau} \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{d^2\boldsymbol{\rho}}{dt^2} = \boldsymbol{\rho}'' \dot{\tau}^2 + \boldsymbol{\rho}' \ddot{\tau} \quad (9)$$

Taking the second derivative of Eq. (4) with respect to t and solving for $\boldsymbol{\rho}''$ allows us to write the equations of motion with respect to the nondimensional time τ in the RPF [19]:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\rho}'' = & -\frac{\ell}{\dot{\tau}} \left[\left(\frac{2\dot{\ell}}{\ell} + \frac{\ddot{\tau}}{\dot{\tau}} \right) \mathbf{I}_3 + 2\mathbf{C}^\top \dot{\mathbf{C}} \right] \boldsymbol{\rho}' - \frac{1}{\dot{\tau}^2} \left[\frac{\ddot{\ell}}{\ell} \mathbf{I}_3 + \frac{2\dot{\ell}}{\ell} \mathbf{C}^\top \dot{\mathbf{C}} + \mathbf{C}^\top \ddot{\mathbf{C}} \right] \boldsymbol{\rho} \\ & + \frac{1}{\ell \dot{\tau}^2} \mathbf{C}^\top (\ddot{\mathbf{r}} - \ddot{\mathbf{b}}) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{I}_3 is the 3×3 identity matrix. Equation (10) can be rearranged in the following form:

$$\boldsymbol{\rho}'' = \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} m_1 \\ m_2 \\ m_3 \end{bmatrix}}_{=:\mathbf{m}_1} + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} m_4 & m_5 & 0 \\ -m_5 & m_4 & m_6 \\ 0 & -m_6 & m_4 \end{bmatrix}}_{=:\mathbf{M}_2} \boldsymbol{\rho}' + \underbrace{\begin{bmatrix} m_7 & m_9 & m_8 \\ -m_9 & m_{10} & m_{11} \\ m_8 & -m_{11} & m_{12} \end{bmatrix}}_{=:\mathbf{M}_3} \boldsymbol{\rho} + m_{13} \nabla \Omega \quad (11)$$

with the potential function

$$\Omega = \frac{\mu_{P_1}}{\|\boldsymbol{\rho} - \boldsymbol{\rho}_{P_1}\|} + \frac{\mu_{P_2}}{\|\boldsymbol{\rho} - \boldsymbol{\rho}_{P_2}\|} + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{A}} \frac{\mu_j}{\|\boldsymbol{\rho} - \boldsymbol{\rho}_j\|} \quad (12)$$

μ_{P_1} , μ_{P_2} , and μ_j denote the nondimensional gravitational parameters of the two primaries and the additional perturbing bodies in the set \mathcal{A} . The sum of the dimensional gravitational parameters of the two primaries is used to nondimensionalize the quantities. The vectors $\boldsymbol{\rho}_{P_1}$, $\boldsymbol{\rho}_{P_2}$, and $\boldsymbol{\rho}_j$ refer to the (nondimensional) positions of the primaries and other bodies in the RPF. The potential functions

associated with the different models are provided in Table 1, where ρ_S and μ_S are the nondimensional position and gravitational parameter of the Sun in the BCRFBP, respectively (assuming a Sun-perturbed Earth-Moon system).

Comparing Eqs. (10) and (11) yields the coefficients m_1 to m_{13} :

$$\mathbf{m}_1 = -\frac{1}{\ell \dot{\tau}^2} \mathbf{C}^\top \ddot{\mathbf{b}} \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_2 = -\frac{\ell}{\dot{\tau}} \left[\left(\frac{2\dot{\ell}}{\ell} + \frac{\ddot{\tau}}{\dot{\tau}} \right) \mathbf{I}_3 + 2 \mathbf{C}^\top \dot{\mathbf{C}} \right] \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{M}_3 = -\frac{1}{\dot{\tau}^2} \left[\frac{\ddot{\ell}}{\ell} \mathbf{I}_3 + \frac{2\dot{\ell}}{\ell} \mathbf{C}^\top \dot{\mathbf{C}} + \mathbf{C}^\top \ddot{\mathbf{C}} \right] \quad (15)$$

$$m_{13} = \frac{\tilde{\mu}_{P_1} + \tilde{\mu}_{P_2}}{\ell^3 (\dot{\tau})^2} \quad (16)$$

where $\tilde{\mu}_{P_1}$ and $\tilde{\mu}_{P_2}$ are the dimensional gravitational parameters of the two primaries. Relevant derivatives can be found in [20]. For the CRTBP, all coefficients are zero except for

$$m_5 = 2 \quad (17)$$

$$m_7 = m_{10} = m_{13} = 1 \quad (18)$$

With regard to the BCRFBP, m_5, m_7, m_{10} , and m_{13} take the same values as in the CRTBP. In addition, the coefficients m_1 and m_2 are non-zero as well [19]:

$$m_1 = -\frac{\mu_S}{\rho_S^2} \cos \theta_S \quad (19)$$

$$m_2 = -\frac{\mu_S}{\rho_S^2} \sin \theta_S \quad (20)$$

θ_S is the Sun angle measured counter-clockwise between $\hat{\mathbf{i}}_x$ and ρ_S , and $\rho_S = \|\rho_S\|$. Unlike previous work [21], and similar to [19], we use a non-constant time scaling factor for the ephemeris model that depends on the instantaneous distance ℓ between the primaries. Consequently, $m_{13} \equiv 1$ at all times, which is consistent with the CRTBP and BCRFBP. Therefore,

$$\dot{\tau} = \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{\mu}_{P_1} + \tilde{\mu}_{P_2}}{\ell^3}} \quad (21)$$

and

$$\ddot{\tau} = -\frac{3}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{\mu}_{P_1} + \tilde{\mu}_{P_2}}{\ell^5}} \dot{\ell} \quad (22)$$

As the distance between the primaries is given by ephemeris for a given physical time t , Eq. (21) can be integrated to obtain the corresponding nondimensional time τ . In this work, we precompute the values of t and τ on a sufficiently fine grid and use interpolation to obtain the desired values. This reduces the computational effort during the integration of the dynamics, as Eq. (21) does not need to be integrated again.

Equation (11) allows us to represent the CRTBP, BCRFBP, and the rotating-pulsating n-body ephemeris model (RPNBP) by simply using different expressions for the coefficients m_1 to m_{13} and by exchanging the potential function in Table 1. This enables a transition between the models by gradually changing the coefficients and potential function, as explained in the next section.

Table 1: Potential functions Ω in the hierarchical equations of motion in Eq. (11).

CRTBP	$\frac{\mu_{P_1}}{\ \rho - \rho_{P_1}\ } + \frac{\mu_{P_2}}{\ \rho - \rho_{P_1}\ }$
BCRFBP	$\frac{\mu_{P_1}}{\ \rho - \rho_{P_1}\ } + \frac{\mu_{P_2}}{\ \rho - \rho_{P_1}\ } + \frac{\mu_S}{\ \rho - \rho_S\ }$
RPNBP	$\frac{\mu_{P_1}}{\ \rho - \rho_{P_1}\ } + \frac{\mu_{P_2}}{\ \rho - \rho_{P_1}\ } + \sum_{j \in \mathcal{A}} \frac{\mu_j}{\ \rho - \rho_j\ }$

HOMOTOPIC APPROACH TO TRANSITION TO HIGHER-FIDELITY MODELS

Indirect methods often utilize a homotopic approach to enhance convergence by solving a sequence of simpler problems, where each solution serves as the initial guess for the subsequent problem [22, 23]. This process is repeated until the original problem is solved. A similar approach can be applied to direct methods, starting with a simplified problem (e.g., two-body dynamics) and using its solution as the basis for solving a higher-fidelity problem (e.g., n-body dynamics)

In this work, we propose a homotopy in the rotating-pulsating frame within our convex optimization framework.

Homotopy Method

Transitioning CRTBP solutions directly to an ephemeris model that includes perturbations of the Sun is challenging, and even NLP solvers can struggle to converge. This becomes even more critical for SCP because of the successive convexification process that approximates the highly nonlinear dynamics. Consequently, a method is needed to reliably obtain trajectories in higher-fidelity models once a solution in the CRTBP is known.

In this work, we describe the development of a homotopic method that aids in transitioning from the CRTBP to the RPNBP, by using the dynamic coefficients reported in the hierarchical equations of motion in Eq. 11. However, the proposed method can be applied to transition to any higher-fidelity models such as the ERTBP, BCRFBP, and ephemeris models.

A test case is considered to compute the coefficients in the RPNBP model. Specifically, Earth and Moon are the two primaries, and the solar system planets with the addition of Pluto represent the additional perturbing bodies. As shown in Fig. 2, we consider an example in which we analyze the evolution of the RPNBP coefficients over a time period of 60 days (blue lines). Some coefficients exhibit complex temporal behavior, characterized by oscillatory patterns, while others show monotonic trends or remain constant. The coefficients of the CRTBP model are instead constant (red lines), as reported in Eqs. (17) and (18). The homotopy computation which describes the transition from the simpler CRTBP model to the more complex RPNBP model (green lines) can be expressed as

$$y_i^h = (1 - \varepsilon)y_i^{CRTBP} + \varepsilon y_i^{RPNBP}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n^{coeff} \quad (23)$$

where y_i^{CRTBP} is the curve associated to the i^{th} CRTBP coefficient, y_i^{RPNBP} is the curve associated to the i^{th} RPNBP coefficient, and $\varepsilon \in [0, 1]$ is the homotopy parameter. If $\varepsilon = 0$ or $\varepsilon = 1$, the CRTBP and RPNBP coefficients are retrieved, respectively; instead, if $0 < \varepsilon < 1$, the homotopy is one of the intermediate curves. In the optimization process, the values of y_i^{CRTBP} and y_i^{RPNBP}

are precomputed based on a selected number of points, so that the homotopy values y_i^h are quickly calculated at each time step (purple markers) by interpolating between points.

Figure 2: Example of homotopy method implementation.

In a similar fashion, the gradient of the potential function $\nabla\Omega$ in Eq. (11), which differs across the models and depends on the state of the spacecraft, undergoes a transition from the CRTBP to the RPNBP model. In this case, y_i^{CRTBP} and y_i^{RPNBP} correspond to the 3 components of the $\nabla\Omega$ vector and are directly computed and combined at each time step of the dynamics. The gradient of the potential function $\nabla\Omega$ includes contributions from the primaries as well as the perturbing bodies; since the contribution from the primaries is the same in both models, this effectively results in incorporating the perturbations from the non-primary bodies with weight ε (since the contributions of the primary bodies to the potential is the same in all models). An important distinction between the components of $\nabla\Omega$ and the dynamics coefficients is that they cannot be precomputed for a fixed timespan, because of their dependence on the state of the spacecraft.

Flowchart of Homotopic Approach

The specific method in which the homotopic model is used to improve convergence in a higher-fidelity model involves slowly stepping up the homotopic parameter to transition to this model from a low-fidelity one. Figure 3 shows the method in which this is done, where a low-fidelity model in which convergence is fast and easy to achieve (such as the CRTBP) is mapped to $\varepsilon = 0$ and a higher-fidelity model (such as the RPNBP) is mapped to $\varepsilon = 1$. Once the problem is set up, the initial guess, typically in the low-fidelity model (since it needs to converge in this) is optimized in that model with a relatively loose tolerance. This is more efficient than solving each successive solution to high tolerance, because it requires fewer iterations, and the intermediate solutions (i.e., $0 < \varepsilon < 1$) are not physically meaningful.

Once the solver converges for a new iteration, the homotopic parameter ε is increased linearly and the solver tolerance is tightened exponentially. If the solver does not converge, the homotopic parameter is decreased linearly and tolerances are loosened exponentially. Additionally, the trust-region radius is increased for the convexified problem in order to expand the search space, in case the failed step moved too far away from the solution. Note that if the solver fails to converge for $\varepsilon = 0$, a better initial guess is required. The decrease amount (in failure-to-converge) must be lesser than the increase amount during convergence since otherwise, the solver is simply solving the last problem again. The solver finally returns a usable solution once it converges for $\varepsilon = 1.0$, i.e. once the model has been completely transitioned to the high-fidelity model. This approach leaves several parameters to tune:

- **Step size of ε :** Reducing this value makes the transition-speed slower, increasing runtime. This should be set maximally such that there are not repeated failures to converge. We used a step-up size of 0.1 and a step-down size of 0.05.
- **Tolerance reduction rate:** Generally, a target for the final tolerance is part of requirements. The reduction rate and initial tolerances are selected to result in the final tolerance (based on the expected number of homotopy steps, based on the ε step size) meeting the requirement. Note that "tolerance" refers to three-separate tolerances here: step-tolerance, optimality-tolerance, and feasibility-tolerance, all of which have relevant parameters selected in the same way. We had desired tolerances of 10^{-9} , 10^{-4} , and 10^{-7} for these respectively, which were achieved with initial tolerances of 10^{-3} , 10^{-1} , and 10^{-2} with reduction rates of $10^{-\frac{6}{10}}$, $10^{-\frac{3}{10}}$, and $10^{-\frac{5}{10}}$ since the expected number of homotopy steps was 10. Note that while tolerance tightening is optional (the strictest tolerance can be used for all steps generally), we were able to achieve a ten times reduction in runtime with this approach.

- **Trust-region radius increase size:** The amount the trust-region should grow when a homotopic step fails to converge should be just enough that a missed solution is included. This means that it should be set minimally and increased if the solver repeatedly fails to converge.

Figure 3: Flowchart of the homotopic approach.

Sequential Convex Programming

In the trust-region-based SCP method used in this work, a series of convexified optimal control problems is solved through successive linearization until the solution satisfies the original nonlinear constraints [24, 25]. The convexified problem is given by

$$\underset{u_i}{\text{minimize}} \quad \sum_{i=1}^{n_u} \|\mathbf{u}_i\|^2 + \lambda \|\boldsymbol{\nu}\|_1 \quad (24a)$$

$$\text{subject to:} \quad \mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) \quad (24b)$$

$$\|\mathbf{u}_i\| \leq \Delta v_{\max} \quad (24c)$$

$$\|\mathbf{x} - \bar{\mathbf{x}}\|_1 \leq R \quad (24d)$$

$$\mathbf{x}(t_0) = \mathbf{x}_0 \quad (24e)$$

$$\mathbf{x}(t_f) = \mathbf{x}_f \quad (24f)$$

where \mathbf{x} are the states, \mathbf{u}_i the impulsive controls, n_u is the number of maneuvers, λ some positive scaling factor for the slack variables $\boldsymbol{\nu}$, $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{u}_i)$ the dynamics linearized about the solution from the previous iteration, Δv_{\max} the maximum control magnitude for each impulsive maneuver, R the trust-region radius to restrict the search space to the neighborhood of the reference solution $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$, and \mathbf{x}_0 and \mathbf{x}_f denote the prescribed initial and final boundary conditions, respectively.

Maneuvers are allowed at the discretization nodes. The linearized and discretized dynamics are then given by

$$\mathbf{x}_{k+1} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{A}_k \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{B}_k \mathbf{u}_k + \mathbf{q}_k + \boldsymbol{\nu}_k, & \text{if } \mathbf{u}_k \neq \mathbf{0} \text{ at } t_k \\ \mathbf{A}_k \mathbf{x}_k + \mathbf{q}_k + \boldsymbol{\nu}_k, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

where $(\cdot)_k := (\cdot)(t_k)$, $k = 1, \dots, N-1$, and N denotes the number of discretization points. $\boldsymbol{\nu}_k$ is an unbounded virtual control to avoid artificial infeasibility and ease convergence. If $\mathbf{u}_k \neq \mathbf{0}$, there is an impulsive maneuver at t_k , and $\mathbf{B}_k \equiv [\mathbf{0}_3, \mathbf{I}_3]^\top$ with the 3×3 zero and identity matrices $\mathbf{0}_3$ and \mathbf{I}_3 , respectively. Moreover,

$$\mathbf{A}_k = \Phi(t_{k+1}, t_k) \quad (26a)$$

$$\mathbf{q}_k = \mathbf{A}_k \int_{t_k}^{t_{k+1}} \Phi^{-1}(t, t_k) \mathbf{q}(t) dt \quad (26b)$$

where $\Phi(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the state transition matrix, and $\mathbf{q}(t) = \mathbf{f}(\bar{\mathbf{x}}, t) - \mathbf{f}_x \bar{\mathbf{x}}$ the constant part of the linearization of the dynamics \mathbf{f} . $\bar{\mathbf{x}}$ denotes the reference state, and \mathbf{f}_x the Jacobian matrix:

$$\mathbf{f}_x = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_3 & \mathbf{I}_3 \\ \mathbf{M}_3 + m_{13} \frac{\partial}{\partial \boldsymbol{\rho}} \nabla \Omega & \mathbf{M}_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (27)$$

where

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \boldsymbol{\rho}} \nabla \Omega = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{S}} \mu_j \left[-\frac{\mathbf{I}_3}{\|\boldsymbol{\rho} - \boldsymbol{\rho}_j\|^3} + \frac{3(\boldsymbol{\rho} - \boldsymbol{\rho}_j)(\boldsymbol{\rho} - \boldsymbol{\rho}_j)^\top}{\|\boldsymbol{\rho} - \boldsymbol{\rho}_j\|^5} \right] \quad (28)$$

The set \mathcal{S} is comprised of the primaries and perturbing bodies. The matrix \mathbf{A}_k and vector \mathbf{q}_k are obtained by integrating the state transition matrix and nonlinear dynamics simultaneously from t_k to t_{k+1} using a 4(5) Runge-Kutta integrator. More details on the SCP algorithm can be found in [24, 25].

SIMULATION AND RESULTS

Two examples are provided in which the homotopic approach results in convergence in the RPNBP model which cannot be achieved without using this approach. The first example involves the Earth-Moon system, where solar perturbations cause a guess trajectory that converges in the CRTBP to fail in the RPNBP. The second example demonstrates the homotopic approach for a two-impulse Earth-to-Moon transfer in the Sun-Earth system, perturbed by the Moon. These examples illustrate the versatility of the homotopic approach in addressing challenging optimization problems that arise due to high-fidelity model complexities.

All simulations are performed in Python, and we use CVXPY [26] to solve the convex problems. Epochs are reported in Barycentric Dynamical Time (TDB).

Sun-Perturbed Earth-Moon System

The primary advantage of the homotopic approach formulated is the ability to slowly transition between a low-fidelity and high-fidelity model when simply using an initial guess which converges in (and was potentially generated with) the low-fidelity model for the high-fidelity model fails to converge. This may occur if the trajectory being analyzed passes through states which are highly perturbed or influenced by factors only present in the high-fidelity model. For example, a guess from the CRTBP may not converge in the RPNBP because perturbations from the sun are significant and push the spacecraft too far off-course for the solver to handle.

Our first example is a heteroclinic-like transfer in the CRTBP, as shown with the dashed line in Fig. 4, between periodic orbits around Lagrange points L_1 and L_2 . This trajectory involves having a spacecraft initially follow the unstable manifold of the L_1 periodic orbit before transitioning onto the stable manifold of the L_2 periodic orbit; it is a ballistic transfer which often serves as a good initial guess for low-energy transfers (such as that in the problem). While directly passing this working trajectory as a guess into the SCP for the RPNBP (i.e., initializing $\varepsilon = 1.0$) works, perturbing the guess slightly by scaling down the initial velocity results in a trajectory which is too difficult for the SCP to optimize in the RPNBP directly, but it is still able to optimize in the CRTBP. The orange line in the same figure represents this perturbed trajectory. In the figure, it can be seen that the perturbation results in a trajectory which does not reach the desired final state, or is infeasible for the problem posed; this is meant to be corrected by the solver. In the case where only this perturbed guess was available, it is desirable to be able to attain an optimized solution that reaches the desired endpoint in the RPNBP.

Table 2: Simulation parameters for Sun-Perturbed Earth-Moon system scenario.

Data	Value
Initial Epoch	1 June 2024 00:00:00 TDB
Time of Flight (days)	23.57
x_0 (-)	[0.870183, -0.059444, 0, -0.010471, -0.175136, 0]
x_f (-)	[1.11559, -0.056398, 0, -0.008555, 0.157211, 0]
Δv_{\max} (-)	0.05

Figure 4: Perturbation of Optimal CRTBP Trajectory.

Running the optimizer using this perturbed guess and applying the procedure from Fig. 3, where the low-fidelity model is the CRTBP and the high-fidelity model is the RPNBP, results in a feasible and optimal solution in the RPNBP. This is illustrated in Fig. 5, where the dashed line represents the infeasible initial guess, and intermediate results of the solver are shown. The problem parameters used are in Table 2. Note that the length and time units are constant in the CRTBP, but transition to time-varying ones in the RPNBP as explained in the problem section.

Figure 5: L_1 - L_2 transfer optimized using homotopic approach.

To better understand the impact of this approach, Fig. 6a presents the trajectories in the x - y plane. It can be seen that the optimizer appears to converge after the first iteration of the homotopy parameter (i.e., solving in the CRTBP). However, viewing the same optimization in the x - z plane,

as shown in Fig. 6b, reveals the gradually-shifting nature of the homotopic approach. It becomes evident that, as expected, the process allows the optimizer to slowly account for perturbations introduced by the Sun which manifest primarily in the z -dimension, for example due to differences in the orbital inclinations. As a result, the orbit extends further into the z -dimension as the homotopy parameter increases while maintaining a similar path in the $x - y$ plane.

Figure 6: Optimization of perturbed trajectory.

This example illustrates that the homotopic approach can be used to solve problems in a high-fidelity model which could not originally be addressed with direct optimization. While this particular case is rather specific, the methodology can be generalized to other transfers where perturbations prevent direct solver convergence in the RPNBP. The gradual adjustment of ϵ and solver tolerances, as outlined in Fig. 3 effectively allows a slow transition between the two which the solver can handle.

Moon-Perturbed Sun-Earth System

Initial Guess Generation We test the homotopic approach in the Moon-Perturbed Sun-Earth system with Earth-Moon ballistic transfers. These transfer trajectories are first generated in the Sun-Earth CRTBP following the approach outlined by Scheuerle et al. (2020) [27]. This method relies on leveraging dynamical structures in the CRTBP and propagating transfers to determine if they reach a periapsis at the orbit radius of the Moon about the Earth.

A Poincaré map is a tool used in dynamical systems theory to analyze periodic, quasi-periodic, and chaotic behavior by capturing the intersection points of a trajectory with a lower-dimensional surface. Starting points for trajectories are discretized on a circular parking orbit about the Earth in the Sun-Earth CRTBP frame. For each starting point, a ΔV is applied in the direction of the velocity, with the magnitude of the ΔV set such that the Jacobi Constant is uniform for all trajectories. The initial conditions of the points are propagated until their trajectories reach periapsis.

(a) Periapse Poincaré map.

(b) Trajectories corresponding to the red dots in the Poincaré map.

(c) Family of lunar transfers across values of Jacobi constant in the Sun-Earth CRTBP.

(d) Guess and perturbed guess trajectory for Sun-Earth system optimization.

Figure 7: Initial guess search with $C = 3.000645$.

While periapsis in the two-body problem is defined as the point of an orbit closest to its central body, Villac and Scheeres (2003) define periapsis in the three-body problem as the point of closest approach [28]. Where q is the velocity of the spacecraft relative to the smaller primary, and v is its speed, periapsis is defined as:

$$\begin{cases} q^\top \dot{q} = 0 & \text{and } q \neq 0, \\ v^2 + q^\top \ddot{q} > 0 \end{cases} \quad (29)$$

For this example's initial guess search, we use Jacobi constant $C = 3.000645$. The initial search utilizing the Poincaré map is shown in Fig. 7a where the periapsis locations of trajectories are plotted in the $x - y$ plane. Periapsides in red, within 40 km to the orbit radius of the Moon, represented by the black circle in Fig. 7 are recorded as our initial guess transfers. Those trajectories with valid periapsis are plotted in Fig. 7b. We choose the trajectory largely in quadrant 4 and plot a family of trajectories with evenly spaced Jacobi constant in Fig. 7c.

Table 3: Simulation parameters for Moon-Perturbed Sun-Earth system scenario.

Data	Value
Initial Epoch	20 March 2024 09:39:03 TDB
Time of Flight, t_f (days)	79.08
x_0 (-)	$[0.999621, 2.630\ 230 \times 10^{-5}, 0, -0.223100, -0.295341, 0]$
x_f (-)	$[1.001756, 0.001880, 0, -0.029967, 0.028039, 0]$
Δv_{\max} (-)	0.05

The initial guess is "perturbed" by being repropagated in the BCRFBP as the new trajectory will not reach the desired end state as shown in Fig. 7d. The start epoch is determined by finding the date of the time of the moon's closest approach to the final state and then subtracting by the time-of-flight. The perturbed guess is run in the optimizer following the procedure from Fig. 3, where the low-fidelity model is the CRTBP and the high-fidelity model is the RPNBP. The initial guess fails to converge directly in RPNBP while the homotopic approach results in a feasible and optimal solution in the RPNBP.

For this specific example and epoch, whose simulation parameters are listed in Table 3, the model is nearly identical to the RPNBP by $\varepsilon = 0.4$ as shown in Fig. 8a. The difference in trajectory between the models is largely in the z axis as shown in Fig. 8b. The optimizer displays similar behavior in this case to the halo orbit example as the gradual change in the model allows the optimizer to adapt to the perturbations from the Moon.

Figure 8: Ballistic lunar transfer optimized using homotopic approach.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, we demonstrate and assess the use of SCP for designing trajectories in different dynamical models. A homotopic approach allows us to gradually transition from the CRTBP to

higher-fidelity models, enhancing convergence. This is demonstrated for examples in which the initial guess fails to converge when directly corrected in the high-fidelity model, but the corrected trajectory is successfully recovered via the homotopic approach. Two examples are provided: one with transfers in the vicinity of the Moon where the next major perturber is the Sun, and one with an Earth-to-Moon transfer leveraging solar gravity, where the next major perturber is the Moon.

The new approach in this work demonstrates strong potential for extending the capabilities of current convex optimization techniques in the context of high-fidelity astrodynamics. High accuracy and robustness and especially speed make SCP an attractive alternative to nonlinear programming solvers, even for highly nonlinear problems, so long as the sequential correction process is appropriately facilitated. The homotopic approach in this work is one example of this. Future work will focus on investigating more challenging examples in the n -body ephemeris model and the rotating-pulsating frame, as well as a more thorough investigation of how the homotopic approach enhances the domain of SCP solver convergence.

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